

A NOTE ON SOLUBILITY METHOD OF DETERMINING DISSOCIATION CONSTANT

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Dhar (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **35**, 800) has deduced the formula

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 \cdot a \cdot (c - b + a)}{(b - a)^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

for the dissociation of weak acids. This has been verified by several workers for monobasic acids, notably by Dhar and Datta (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1913, **19**, 407), Bhagawat and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 807), Bhagwat and Doosaj (*ibid.*, 1933, **10**, 477) and by Bhagwat (*ibid.*, 1939, **16**, 235). This work was extended to dibasic acids by Datta and Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 824) and they modified the equation. They showed :—

$$K_2 = K_1 \cdot \frac{a[c - 2(b - a)]}{(b - a)^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

In our opinion the formula seems to require modification. Consider the reaction with CO_2 solution, that is with H_2CO_3 , then we have

Let c be the initial concentration of CH_3COONa , a be the solubility of CO_2 in water and b be the solubility of CO_2 in CH_3COONa of concentration, c , then the excess $b - a$ goes to form CH_3COOH and NaHCO_3 . Hence finally the moles of CH_3COOH and NaHCO_3 formed are $(b - a)$ and $(b - a)$. Thus finally the

conc. of $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa} = c - (b - a)$; conc. of $\text{CH}_3\text{COO}' = c - (b - a)$,
(complete ionisation is assumed)

„ H_2CO_3 a does not ionise.
„ CH_3COOH $b - a$ „ „ „
„ NaHCO_3 $b - a = \text{HCO}_3'$ ionises completely.

Now we know that for dissociation constant of acetic acid K_2 we have

$$K_2 = \frac{\text{CH}_3\text{COO}' \times \text{H}'}{\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}} \quad \dots (a) \quad \text{also } K_1 = \frac{\text{H}' \times \text{HCO}_3'}{\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3} \quad \dots (b)$$

Eliminating H' and substituting the values we have

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 \cdot a \cdot (c - b + a)}{(b - a)^2} \quad \dots (3)$$

This equation is the same as (1) and not as (2). Moreover, if we assume the reaction to be

The molar conc. of CH_3COOH formed $= 2(b - a)$
„ „ Na_2CO_3 $= b - a = \text{CO}_3''$
„ „ CH_3COONa (left) $= c - 2(b - a) = \text{CH}_3\text{COO}'$
„ „ H_2CO_3 $= a$

then as before

$$K_2 = \frac{H^{\bullet} \times CH_3COO'}{CH_3COOH} \quad \dots (a)$$

But here the conc. of H (ion) cannot be determined as before for we only know

$$\frac{H^{\bullet} \times HCO_3'}{H_2CO_3} = K_1 \text{ (first dissociation).}$$

and

$$\frac{H^{\bullet} \times CO_3''}{HCO_3'} = K_1' \text{ (second dissociation).}$$

But we only know CO_3'' and H_2CO_3 , but not HCO_3' concentration. We have from above

$$\frac{H^{\bullet 2} \times CO_3''}{H_2CO_3} = K_1 \cdot K_1'$$

or

$$H^{\bullet 2} = \frac{K_1 \cdot K_1' \cdot a}{(b-a)}$$

Substituting the values in (a)

$$K_2 = \sqrt{K_1 \cdot K_1' \cdot \frac{a}{(b-a)} \left\{ \frac{c-2(b-a)}{2(b-a)} \right\}}$$

or

$$K_2 = \frac{\sqrt{K_1 \cdot K_1'}}{2} \frac{\sqrt{a} \{c-2(b-a)\}}{(b-a) \sqrt{(b-a)}} \quad \dots (4)$$

Even this deduction is different from (2). The author is forced to conclude therefore that the equation of Datta and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) seems to be incorrect.

It will be clear therefore that if we are finding the dissociation constant of a monobasic acid by taking its sodium or potassium salt with the help of a weak acid say n -basic then if we assume the dissociation of the acid H_nB as

so that

then we have K_2 as

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 \cdot a \cdot (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$$

If the dissociation is complete then $H_nB \rightarrow nH + B''$

so that $nCH_3COONa + H_nB = nCH_3COOH + Na_nB$

$$\text{then } K_2 = \sqrt[n]{\frac{K_1 \cdot K_1' \cdot K_1'' \dots n \text{ factors.}}{n}} \cdot \frac{\sqrt[n]{a} \{c-n(b-a)\}}{(b-a) \sqrt[n]{(b-a)}}$$

If the acid whose dissociation constant is required is also m -basic and we take the salt Na_mA for this acid H_mA , then if the reaction is

then we have

$$A'^m = c - b + a \text{ and } HA'^{n-1} = b - a$$

also

$$K_m = \frac{H' \cdot A'^m}{HA'^{m-1}}, \text{ the } m^{\text{th}} \text{ dissociation constant of the acid. Hence}$$

the formula

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 \cdot a \cdot (c - b + a)}{(b - a)^2} \quad \dots (5)$$

gives m^{th} dissociation constant provided K_1 is the first dissociation constant where,

$$K_1 = \frac{H' \cdot H_{n-1} B'}{H_n B} \text{ of the acid } H_n B.$$

If the reaction is as

Then we have concentration of $H_n B = a$ and that of $B'^n = (b - a)$

$$H_m A = \frac{n}{m} (b - a)$$

$$A'^m = c - \frac{n}{m} (b - a) = \frac{mc - n(b - a)}{m}$$

We have for an acid

$$\frac{B'^n}{H_n B} \cdot H'^n = K_1 \cdot K_1' \cdot K_2'' \dots \text{to } n \text{ factors.}$$

or

$$H' = \sqrt[n]{K_1 \cdot K_1' \cdot K_1'' \dots n \text{ factors}} \sqrt[n]{\frac{a}{(b - a)}} \quad \dots (x)$$

Similarly

$$\frac{A'^m}{H_m A} \cdot H'^m = K_2 \cdot K_2' \cdot K_2'' \dots K_m \dots n \text{ factors.}$$

or

$$H' = \sqrt[m]{K_2 \cdot K_2' \cdot K_2'' \dots m \text{ factors}} \sqrt[m]{\frac{n(b - a)}{mc - n(b - a)}} \quad \dots (y)$$

Hence for equilibrium, equation (x) = equation (y)

or

$$\begin{aligned} & \sqrt[n]{K_1 \cdot K_1' \cdot K_1'' \dots n \text{ factors}} \sqrt[n]{\frac{a}{(b - a)}} \\ &= \sqrt[m]{K_2 \cdot K_2' \cdot K_2'' \dots m \text{ factors}} \sqrt[m]{\frac{n(b - a)}{mc - n(b - a)}} \quad \dots (6) \end{aligned}$$

Clearly this formula does not allow us to calculate the dissociation constants but establishes a relationship among them.

If $m = 1$ and $n = 1$ then

$$K_1 \cdot \frac{a}{(b - a)} = \frac{(b - a)}{c - (b - a)} \cdot K_2$$

or

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 \cdot a \cdot (c - b + a)}{(b - a)^2}$$

the same formula as given in (1)

If $n = 2$ and $m = 1$

$$K_2 \frac{2(b-a)}{c-2(b-a)} = \sqrt{K_1 \cdot K_1'} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{a}{(b-a)}}$$

or

$$K_2 = \frac{\sqrt{K_1 \cdot K_1'}}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{a}{(b-a)} \cdot \frac{c-2(b-a)}{(b-a)}}$$

the same as equation (4).

Doosaj and Bhagwat (*loc. cit.*) have investigated the limits of application of this formula. From theoretical considerations they have established equations which show that the solubility method shows maximum accuracy when the dissociation constants of the acids employed are identical, or are more or less of the same order. These results are supported by their work.

It must be emphasised that in all cases it is assumed that the ionisation of a salt is complete and that of a weak acid is near about zero.

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Erratum

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